

ELIXIR Commissioned Service Report for Milestones

Document info

Title	Training SPLASH website made public
Deliverable/Milestone Number	M2.9
Responsible Participant	Alexander Botzki
WP Number	WP2
Dissemination level (PU/RE/CO / or NA)	PU

*For types of deliverables please see [Guidelines for ELIXIR Commissioned Services](#)

Version history

Version	Revised by	Date	Comment
0.1	draft	08/11/2024	
1.0.0	Alexander Botzki	23/12/2024	
1.0.1	SPLASH project leads: Alex Botzki Alexia Cardona Elin Kronander Geert Van Geest Bruna Piereck Moura	29/01/2025	
	Content Check by WP1	07/02/2025	ok'ed during ExCo call
	Admin Check by Hub (CoS Portfolio Manager)		(To revise section X)
	Content Check by Hub (Programme Manager)		

Author List

Node (ISO 2 letter country code or (eg: EMBL-EBI))	Institute (no address)	Name, surname	ORCID	Email
UK	UNICAM	Alexia Cardona	0000-0002-7877-5565	ac812@cam.ac.uk
SE	UU/NBIS	Elin Kronander	0000-0003-0280-6318	elin.kronander@scilifelab.se
BE	VIB	Alex Botzki	0000-0001-6691-4233	alexander.botzki@vib.be
BE	VIB	Bruna Piereck Moura	0000-0001-5958-0669	bruna.piereckmoura@vib.be
CH	SIB	Geert van Geest	0000-0002-1561-078X	Geert.Vangeest@sib.swiss
ES	BSC	Eva Alloza	0000-0001-8385-9336	eva.alloza@bsc.es
SE	NBIS	Jessica Lindvall	0000-0002-5042-8481	jessica.lindvall@scilifelab.se
GR	CERTH	Fotis Psomopoulos	0000-0002-0222-4273	fpsom@certh.gr

Abbreviations and Acronyms

(Remove if not applicable)

ETrP	ELIXIR Training Platform
------	--------------------------

Contents

Document info	1
Version history	1
Author List	3
Abbreviations and Acronyms	4
Executive Summary	6
Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone	6

Executive Summary

The ELIXIR SPLASH project aims to centralize and highlight the diverse training resources developed by ETrP. By creating a user-friendly digital platform, SPLASH seeks to raise awareness and recognition of training efforts and ensure sustainable, high-quality training practices. The objective is to enhance accessibility and ensure the long-term impact of ETrP resources by creating a "one-stop-shop" platform. The problem addressed is the dispersion of training resources across various channels, making it difficult to maintain a comprehensive and consistent training approach. The project has been kickstarted at the BioHackathon 2023 - [project 34](#).

Milestone M2.9 marks the public launch of the ELIXIR SPLASH project website, a centralized digital resource showcasing the diverse training products and resources developed by the ELIXIR Training Platform (ETrP).

The milestone was successfully achieved following several discussions and workshops with the Training Platform and Training Coordinators. Key meetings included the WP2 monthly meetings, SPLASH review meetings, and joint content/technical meetings. The content of the Training Lifecycle stages and relevant ELIXIR resources, such as the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer programme, Learning Paths project, and FAIR training project, are now displayed on the SPLASH website. Future workshops are planned to develop checklists for each stage of the training lifecycle and add new relevant resources.

By centralizing these resources, the SPLASH project ensures that training is not only accessible but also adheres to the highest educational standards, fostering sustainable and impactful training programs in the life sciences.

Outcomes and Impacts of the milestone

Milestone *M2.9 Training SPLASH website made public* is part of the SPLASH project. Cornerstones for this milestone were the completion of several other milestones following an editorial meeting of the SPLASH editorial team on December 18th, 2024 (see [M3.1 Consolidate the key components of the ELIXIR Training lifecycle by discussions with Training Excos and Training Coordinators](#), see [M3.4 Editorial review and feedback of the different documentation and pages on Training SPLASH for content consistency in each page](#), see [M3.2 Create editorial guidelines and template for each component of the training life cycle to follow for content consistency in each page](#)).

The content of the Training lifecycle stages is now displayed on the SPLASH website as well the content of many relevant ELIXIR resources like the ELIXIR-GOBLET Train-the-Trainer programme (see *D4.3 Sections in the Training SPLASH with the data from the TtT Instructors and TtT course feedback and assessments*), the Learning Paths project, FAIR training project, TeSS, the new Training Metrics Database and the e-learning working group.

Figure 1: The Training Lifecycle¹

This milestone was achieved after several discussions and workshops with the Training Platform and Training Coordinators. Workshops included:

- SPLASH kickoff meeting (22 August 2023)
- SPLASH Training Lifecycle brainstorming meeting (6 October 2023)
- Biohackathon Europe 2023 Project: SPLASH Project (20 October -3 November 2023)
- Training Life Cycle Workshop 1 (22 April 2024)
- Training Life Cycle Workshop 2 (3 May 2024)
- WP2 monthly meetings 2024
- SPLASH review meeting (22 November 2024)
- SPLASH joint content/technical meeting 1 (11 December 2024)
- SPLASH joint content/technical meeting 2 (18 December 2024)
- SPLASH Editorial meeting (18 December 2024)
- SPLASH technical monthly meetings 2024

Further workshops are planned to develop checklists for each stage of the training lifecycle, add new relevant resources working towards *D3.1 A homogeneous narrative of the training lifecycle steps, connected to the various documents/SOPs/Best practices.*

¹ <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>